

CYCLIC LOADING TEST AND ANALYTICAL EVALUATION OF CIRCULAR STEEL COLUMNS RETROFITTED BY EXTERNALLY BONDED CARBON FIBER SHEETS IN GRADED CONFIGURATION

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ABSTRACT

In this study, the use of carbon fiber sheets in graded configuration aims to provide an optimal technique to address stress concentrations at the lower regions of the columns. The effect on the circular steel column specimen's horizontal load capacity, energy absorption, and buckling behavior were experimentally and analytically evaluated by subjecting the specimen to a constant axial load and an increasing cyclic lateral load. Analytical results from the implemented finite element analysis models were verified using the experimental results. Two cases were considered: 1) the application of CF sheets on column specimen before loading (reinforcement model) and 2) application of CF sheets after the column specimen have undergone failure (repair model). For the finite element analysis model, the steel column and CF sheets were modeled as structural shell elements. The interaction at the steel and CF sheets interface was considered by accounting for the adhesive stiffness through contact condition analysis. The results showed that the reinforcement model can effectively increase the horizontal load capacity and the repair model can sufficiently retrofit the horizontal load capacity, and the implemented finite element analysis model can adequately evaluate the horizontal loading capacity, energy absorption, and buckling modes of reinforcement and repair models.

KEYWORDS

Seismic retrofitting of steel structures; Carbon fiber sheet; Finite element analysis; Case studies and applications; Circular steel columns

INTRODUCTION

Aside from the lessons learned from the recent 2011 Great Japan East Earthquake and 2016 Kumamoto Earthquake, Japan is currently anticipating the high probability of occurrence of large-scale earthquakes soon since the sources of the Nankai Trough Earthquake and Tokyo Inland Earthquake are now on their active phases. Both events have the likelihood of generating earthquakes of a scale of magnitude 8 or more (Disaster Management, Cabinet Office, 2021). With this, part of the country's medium- and long-term disaster resilience plans are to implement enhancements on the application of technologies in lifeline infrastructure construction and countermeasures for aging structures. Since bridges function as lifeline networks especially during disasters, it is important to maintain the components of this system. Circular steel columns are identified to be susceptible to local buckling or even rupture due to excessive inelastic deformations when subjected to strong lateral loads. In the case of the damages observed after the Kobe Earthquake in 1995, buckling damages were found at various parts of the columns such as the base (elephant foot buckling), third point along the column height, and near structural discontinuity (or stiffness changes) (Bruneau, 1995). Therefore, an effective seismic retrofitting measure shall be implemented to mitigate these issues that can lead to structure collapse. Carbon fiber (CF) sheet wrapping is one of the well-known seismic retrofitting techniques for steel bridge piers utilized to suppress local buckling and delay the onset of plastic deformation.

Despite the advantages of this method, existing studies show that the restraining effect of CF sheets eventually leads to inward buckling modes that causes sudden decrease in the load carrying capacity of columns upon failure (Okazaki et al., 2017). To potentially address this issue, a study showed that CF

sheets in graded configuration lessens inward buckling and maintains the substantial retrofitting effect to the column specimen (Magtagnob et al., 2021). Aside from experimental studies, generating finite element analysis (FEA) models verified using experimental test results can be useful in creating efficient designs with an adequate level of accuracy, especially to establish the design methodology. However, there are still a limited number of analytical studies regarding the use of CF sheet wrapping for retrofitting and performance recovery of steel columns. Hence, in this study, analytical evaluation of the reinforcement and repair effect of CF sheets in graded configuration was conducted. A parametric study was performed to adequately evaluate the steel column specimen's horizontal load capacity, energy absorption, and buckling behavior using FEA. Analytical results from the implemented FEA models were verified using the experimental results from the cyclic loading test conducted in a previous study.

SPECIMEN DESIGN AND EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

This section discusses the dimensions of the specimen, loading program, and CF sheet reinforcement cases that were adopted from an existing study by Magtagnob et al. (2021).

Circular Column Specimen

The considered specimen is a hollow circular steel column (JIS STK400) as shown in Figure 1. Material properties of the steel are presented in Table 1. Stiffening ribs and a thicker section were incorporated into the specimen to prevent buckling near the column base. The specimen is anchored to the ground using 12-M36 bolts tightened by hydraulic bolt tensioning. This unreinforced (N) specimen serves as the benchmark and control set up at which results from the reinforcement and repair cases were evaluated.

Figure 1: Schematic Diagram for Column Steel Specimen

Carbon Fiber Sheet Retrofitting

Two CF sheet retrofitting cases were considered in this study: 1) the application of CF sheets on the column specimen before loading (reinforcement case, R) and 2) the application of CF sheets after the column specimen has undergone failure (repair case, S).

Unidirectional high strength CF sheets (UT70-30G) with tensile stress capacity of 3400 N/mm^2 and modulus of elasticity equal to $245,000 \text{ N/mm}^2$ were utilized as the reinforcement and repair material. CF sheet layers are bonded to the circular steel column using AUP40 epoxy resin via vacuum-assisted resin transfer molding (VaRTM). This method of impregnating the CF sheet layers with resin produces the carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP). The schematic diagram for the VaRTM procedure is shown in Figure 2a, while the 10-4/150-250 graded CF sheet configuration is attached to the steel column as shown in Figure 2b. This graded configuration is comprised of a thick CFRP layer ranging from $h = 300 \text{ mm}$ to $h = 450 \text{ mm}$ with 10 CF sheet layers, and thin CFRP layer ranging from $h = 450 \text{ mm}$ to $h = 700 \text{ mm}$ with 4 CF sheet layers. This arrangement primarily aims to address stress concentrations and suppress local deformations that usually occur at lower regions and stiffness discontinuities of columns.

Loading Program

In the vertical direction, the specimen was subjected to a constant axial load equal to 10% of the

column's yielding axial force (492.9 kN) to represent the superstructure weight. In the horizontal direction, an increasing cyclic lateral load was applied at the top of the specimen by displacement control. The lateral load is composed of increasing increments of the calculated horizontal yield displacement of the column specimen (δ_y) equal to 10 mm. A maximum displacement load of $\pm 9\delta_y$ was applied to determine the resulting behavior at high displacement load cycles and to maximize the maximum stroke of the test equipment.

The implemented loading program varies with the retrofitting case under consideration. The loading program in Figure 3a is applied to the unreinforced (N) and reinforcement (R) cases; however, for the reinforcement case, due to the limitation during the actual experiment, horizontal cyclic loading was only applied until $\pm 8\delta_y$. For the repair case (S), as shown in Figure 3b, the primary loading is applied to the unreinforced specimen until failure is observed at $\pm 6\delta_y$. After the primary loading, the specimen was unloaded to 0 kN, followed by the CF sheet repair. Subsequently, secondary loading was applied consistent with the program used for the unreinforced and reinforcement cases.

Figure 2: CF Sheet Reinforcement Diagram

Figure 3: Loading Program

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The resulting load-displacement envelope curves from the cyclic loading test of each case from the earlier research are illustrated in Figure 4 (Magtagñob et al., 2021). The maximum horizontal load capacity measured for the unreinforced specimen (N-EXP) is 418.4 kN at $+4\delta_y$ for the positive loading side and -417.3 kN at $-4\delta_y$ for the negative loading side. N-EXP reached failure at $\pm 6\delta_y$ at which buckling deformations for both the positive and negative loading sides became prominent. N-EXP1 represents the specimen behavior until failure, while N-EXP2 represents the specimen behavior until maximum loading of $\pm 9\delta_y$.

Figure 4: Summary of Experimental Envelope Curves

The reinforcement specimen (R-EXP) exhibited an increase in both horizontal load capacity and ductility amounting to at least 10% and 35%, respectively. The failure point displacement, wherein the maximum horizontal load capacity post-peak drops to 95%, is used to measure ductility. High values of this displacement entail better ductility of the element. Thus, the graded CF sheet reinforcement is effective in suppressing the buckling deformations that caused N-EXP failure at earlier loading cycles. This can be seen from Figure 5a, which illustrates the N-EXP and R-EXP hysteresis curves.

On the other hand, the repair specimen (S-EXP) exhibited reasonable recovery of the N-EXP horizontal load capacity and ductility even after the specimen had undergone failure and buckling from primary loading. The repair by graded CF sheet configuration can increase the column horizontal load capacity and ductility by 8% and 34% for the positive loading side, respectively. On the negative side, the maximum horizontal load is close to that of N-EXP with a minimal decrease of 2%, while the improvement can be seen in terms of the 8% increase in ductility. For further illustration, Figure 5b shows the superimposed N-EXP and S-EXP hysteresis curves.

Figure 5: Horizontal Load and Displacement Relationship, Experimental Results

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS AND PARAMETRIC STUDY

Finite Element Model

Finite element analysis (FEA) was performed using the large strain nonlinear analysis procedure of the general-purpose finite element program MSC Marc/Mentat 2019. Updated Lagrange, additive decomposition procedure was implemented. Steel elements were modeled using 4-node thick shell elements. On the other hand, the CFRP was modeled using 4-node thin shell elements, as the classical stress-strain relations for this element is similar to that of a unidirectionally reinforced lamina.

Lower regions of the model up to 300 mm above the reinforcement area were modeled using 10 x 20 mm mesh size to accurately capture buckling deformations and stress concentrations. The remaining upper regions are modeled with 20 x 20 mm mesh size for practical purposes. Figure 6 illustrates part of the finite element model constructed in MSC Marc/Mentat 2019.

Figure 6: Finite Element Model

The steel material was modeled using an isotropic elasto-plastic material considering von Mises yield criteria and the kinematic hardening law of plasticity. These simplified models are known to predict the cyclic loading behavior of an element with a relatively good accuracy. Input values for steel plasticity

are based on uniaxial results from coupon tests. The CFRP was modeled using orthotropic material with defined limits to account for the calculated tensile and compressive capacity of the CFRP. The properties of the resulting CFRP from the VaRTM procedure are calculated using the Halpin-Tsai approximate equations with consideration of the upper and lower bound moduli (Jones, 1999). A fiber volume fraction of 50% was assumed in the calculations since studies show that the VaRTM method can produce CFRP with fiber volume fraction ranging from 40 to 50% (Hsiao & Heider, 2012). The bonding between the steel and CFRP elements were modeled using the glued cohesive contact analysis option in MSC Marc/Mentat 2019 wherein the contact stiffness was defined by the properties of the AUP40 resin. The material properties of the steel, CF sheet, epoxy resin, and CFRP are summarized in Table 1.

A parametric study is conducted to generate a finite element model that can adequately represent the cyclic loading of circular steel columns in their unreinforced (N), reinforced (R), and repair cases (S). The finite element models and analysis parameters considered in this study are summarized in Table 2.

Table 1: Material Properties

Material	Properties	Symbols	Values	Units
Steel (JIS STK400)	Elastic modulus	E	190,200	MPa
	Yield stress	σ_y	363	MPa
Carbon Fiber Sheet (UT70-30G)	Elastic modulus (0°)	E_{cfl}	245,000	MPa
	Tensile strength (0°)	$\sigma_{f,t}$	3400	MPa
	Poisson's ratio (0°)	ν_{cfl}	0.2	-
	Design thickness	t_{cf}	0.167	mm
Epoxy Resin (AUP40)	Elastic modulus	E_m	3,430	MPa
	Poisson's ratio	ν_m	0.39	-
CFRP	Fiber content	V_f	50	%
	Thickness (10-layer)	$t_{cfm, 10}$	0.334	mm
	Thickness (4-layer)	$t_{cfm, 4}$	0.134	mm
	Longitudinal Elastic modulus	E_1	111,800	MPa
		E_{1ub}	124,200	MPa
		E_{1lb}	6,800	MPa
	Transverse Elastic modulus	E_2	12,900	MPa
		E_{2ub}	7,800	MPa
		E_{2lb}	5,400	MPa
	Shear modulus	G_{12}	3,600	MPa
Poisson's ratio	ν_{12}	0.29	-	

Table 2: Summary of Models

Parametric Study	Model	Classification	Base Condition (F/O)	Steel Element (S)	Return Mapping Algorithm (P)	CFRP Compression Resistance (C)
Base Condition and Element Modeling	N-FP0	No Reinforcement	Fixed Base	Shell (#75)	Mean-normal	-
	N-OP0	No Reinforcement	Explicit Base	Shell (#75)	Mean-normal	-
	N-OP0S	No Reinforcement	Explicit Base	Solid (#7)	Mean-normal	-
Elasto-Plastic Analysis Procedures for Retrofitting Cases	R-OP0C1	Reinforcement	Explicit Base	Shell (#75)	Mean-normal	Compression Resistant
	R-OP1C1	Reinforcement	Explicit Base	Shell (#75)	Multi-stage Radial Return (RR)	Compression Resistant
	N-OP1	No Reinforcement	Explicit Base	Shell (#75)	Multi-stage RR	-
CFRP Compression Resistance	R-OP1C0	Reinforcement	Explicit Base	Shell (#75)	Multi-stage RR	Non-compression Resistant
	S-OP1C1	Repair	Explicit Base	Shell (#75)	Multi-stage RR	Compression Resistant
	S-OP1C0	Repair	Explicit Base	Shell (#75)	Multi-stage RR	Non-compression Resistant

Base Condition and Element Modeling

In this model, the effects of base conditions and element modeling were examined. Geometric and material properties for this model are based on the considerations defined in the earlier section.

In FEA modeling practice, base conditions are usually assumed to be fixed for simplicity and practical purposes. However, additional base moments may occur for compression elements such as columns caused by relative displacements at the top of the column, also known as the $P-\Delta$ effect. As shown in Figure 7a, $P-\Delta$ effect results to changes in the force displacement characteristics of the element, such as reduction of initial stiffness and lateral force capacity (Pourali et al., 2019).

To capture this behavior, the induced base displacements and moments are considered by explicitly modeling the specimen base conditions, as shown in Fig 7b. The circular base plate was modeled using thick shell elements with a touching contact condition with the ground element. This ensures the simulation of displacements at the base plate without penetrating the ground element. The anchor bolts

were modeled using line elements with a diameter of 36 mm and elastic modulus equal to 210 GPa. Overclosure tying constraints were used to simulate the bolt pre-tension force by applying loads to a control node connected to parts of the bolt element (MSC Software Corporation, 2019). Results from the analysis of unreinforced models with a fixed base (N-FP0) and an explicit base (N-OP0) are shown in Figure 8. It can be observed from the resulting envelope curves that accounting for P- Δ effects results to lower initial stiffness and more gradual strength degradation at the post-peak branch, which better approximates the experimental results compared to the fixed base model. Furthermore, the cyclic loading behavior of N-OP0 is closer to that of the experimental results compared to N-FP0, since N-FP0 resulted in steeper loading and unloading branches. Therefore, it was decided to adopt the explicit base modeling, N-OP0, for the succeeding parametric studies.

Figure 7: Base Condition Modeling Considerations

Figure 8: Base condition model results

The effect of modeling using solid elements was also observed. As an alternative to using thick shell elements (#75), the steel was modeled using 8-node hexahedral elements. As shown in Figure 9, there is a minimal difference in the results from the shell model (N-OP0) and solid model (N-OP0S) in terms of both the horizontal load-displacement envelope and hysteresis curves. Therefore, to maintain the simplicity of the model and practicality in terms of analysis time, the shell model was adopted for the implemented analytical model. Finally, Table 3 summarizes the maximum horizontal displacement capacity of each model and its corresponding percent error with respect to the experimental results. From this, it can be concluded that N-OP0 best approximates the N-EXP results in terms of both the maximum horizontal capacity and the horizontal displacement at which H_{max} occurs.

Figure 9: Shell vs Solid element model results

Table 3: Comparison of maximum horizontal load capacity (Base condition and element modeling)

Model	(+ direction)			(- direction)		
	δ_{max}	H_{max} (kN)	H_{max} % error	δ_{max}	H_{max} (kN)	H_{max} % error
N-EXP1	$+4\delta_v$	418.4	-	$-4\delta_v$	-417.3	-
N-FP0	$+3\delta_v$	413.2	1.2%	$-2\delta_v$	-411.6	1.4%
N-OP0	$+4\delta_v$	416.4	0.5%	$-3\delta_v$	-410.5	1.6%
N-OP0S	$+3.3\delta_v$	403.8	3.5%	$-2.4\delta_v$	-402.8	3.5%

Elasto-plastic Analysis Procedures for Retrofitting Cases

In nonlinear analysis, it is necessary to use appropriate material models to accurately capture the overall behavior of the structure. In addition to these, the numerical implementation used in the analysis is equally important to provide accurate solutions. Since this study is dealing with cyclic elastoplastic behavior at large deformations, the key parameter that can be investigated is the return mapping algorithm considered in the analysis (Scherzinger, 2016). Return mapping algorithms are used to obtain updated stress values with respect to strain variation at each increment to predict the nonlinear behavior (Mano et al., 2022). Furthermore, studies suggest that efficient implementations of return mapping algorithms are necessary to capture failure mechanisms of orthotropic materials that strongly vary with respect to loading or stress directions (Pech et al., 2021).

In this section, the parametric study considers the available return mapping algorithms in MSC Marc/Mentat 2019, namely, the mean-normal method and the multi-stage radial return method. The mean-normal method is the default algorithm used in the program and is usually stable for elasto-plastic behavior analysis; however, additional considerations may be necessary if contact conditions are present, and if buckling is expected. Multistage radial return mapping is generally applied for isotropic and anisotropic large strain analysis. It was also found to provide accurate solutions for the 2D stress version of the anisotropic Barlat models, which can be reduced to the more common Von Mises and Hill models with corresponding setting of parameters (Scherzinger, 2016). With the established Newton-Raphson iteration procedure, applicable return mapping procedures on calculating the stress state of the material for the retrofitting cases are investigated in this section.

The maximum horizontal load capacity and its corresponding error with respect to the experimental results are summarized in Table 4. Also, Figures 10a and 10b show the superimposed cyclic loading curves of the experimental (R-EXP) and analytical cases considering mean-normal method (R-OP0C1) and multi-stage radial return method (R-OP1C1), respectively. Both models exhibit overestimation of the energy absorption capacity of the reinforcement case; however, R-OP1C1 yielded more conservative estimates compared to R-OP0C1, especially at larger displacement increments. R-OP1C1 also has loading and unloading behaviors that better capture the measured cyclic loading behavior of R-EXP. Hence, R-OP1C1 is adopted for the implemented FEA model.

It should also be noted that the adopted model is also implemented and checked for the N-models, since it will be critical for the repair models that are initially analyzed as unreinforced specimen under the primary loading. Shown in Figure 10c are the comparison of the considered N-models. Although the updated N-OP1 exhibits faster strength degradation post peak, it still adequately estimates the initial rigidity, pre-yielding behavior, and maximum horizontal load of N-EXP which are critical for the primary loading and achieving the initial damaged condition for S-models. This also illustrates that the default mean normal method is adequate for modeling the unreinforced steel specimen; however, the multistage radial return mapping became advantageous with the introduction of CFRP with orthotropic properties to the steel specimen. Moreover, the latter effectively captures buckling behavior for all models; this will be further discussed in the succeeding sections of this paper.

Compressive Resistance of CFRP

CFRP is widely known for its high tensile strength, primarily inherent in the CF sheet's characteristics. On the other hand, the compression resistance of the CFRP is a function of the bond between the CF sheet fibers and the impregnating resin, since the resin matrix primarily resists the shearing forces induced by the buckling and misalignments of CF sheet fibers under compression loading. Hence, the estimation of the CFRP's compression resistance is critical to producing an effective model of the column behavior (Mechin et al., 2019).

Figure 10: Elasto-plastic analysis models load-displacement curves

Table 4: Comparison of maximum horizontal load capacity and energy absorption rate (Elasto-plastic analysis models)

Model	(+) direction				(-) direction			
	Maximum Horizontal Load			Energy absorption rate	Maximum Horizontal Load			Energy absorption rate
	δ_{max}	H_{max} (kN)	H_{max} , % error		δ_{max}	H_{max} (kN)	H_{max} , % error	
R-EXP	$+8\delta_y$	479.5	-	1.00	$-7\delta_y$	-462.0	-	1.00
R-0POC1	$+8\delta_y$	491.4	2.5%	1.04	$-8\delta_y$	-490.2	6.1%	1.09
R-0PIC1	$+7\delta_y$	480.4	0.2%	1.03	$-6\delta_y$	-478.8	3.4%	1.06

Table 5: CFRP tensile and compressive capacities

Tensile Capacity			Compressive Capacity		
Symbol	Value	Unit	Symbol	Value	Unit
$\sigma_{c, tmax}$	1722	MPa	$\sigma_{c, cmax}$	1555	MPa
$\epsilon_{c, tmax}$	0.0130	-	$\epsilon_{cr, cmax}$	0.0127	-

In this study, the calculated tensile and compressive strengths of the CFRP as a composite material with unidirectionally reinforced lamina were considered. Tensile strength is based on the combination of the fiber and resin matrix capacities. The compressive strength is based on the shear and transverse failure mode of the resin matrix due to fiber buckling, which are primarily governed by the shear and elastic moduli of the resin matrix (Jones, 1999). Table 5 summarizes the calculated capacities of the resulting CFRP.

In the parametric study, two models were considered to verify the effect of the compression resistance of the CFRP: 1) assuming that the CFRP has no compression resistance (C0), and 2) accounting for the CFRP's compression resistance using approximate equations (C1). These are implemented for both reinforcement (R) and repair (S) models. Upon exceeding the CFRP tensile and compressive capacity limits, CFRP failure was accounted for by the stiffness degradation of the CFRP shell elements. However, as one of the model limitations, the CFRP debonding progress was not captured in the model. R-models were analyzed up to $\pm 8\delta_y$ which is equal to the maximum displacement load applied in the experimental reinforcement case. Due to the difference in analytical and experimental results for the unreinforced case, the primary loading for the S-models was adjusted accordingly. The primary loading applied for the analytical S-models is only up to $\pm 5\delta_y$ since the buckling behavior at this load increment best approximates the damage condition of the unreinforced specimen at $\pm 6\delta_y$.

Figures 11a and 11b show the maximum CFRP stresses at nodes in line with the lateral loading axis. Results for C0 and C1 models were plotted separately to clearly illustrate the stress limits for each case. As expected, C0 models exhibit earlier CFRP failure compared to C1 models. It can be noticed that

strength degradation subsequently occurs after the load increments at which CFRP failure occurs – refer to Figures 11c and 11d for the corresponding envelope curves. Hence, the FEA models were able to capture the decrease in horizontal load capacity and subsequent buckling leading to failure upon exceeding the CFRP capacity, as observed in the experiment.

Figure 11: CFRP Compression Resistance model results

For the reinforcement models, it can be observed from Figure 11c that both R-0P1C1 (compression resistant CFRP) and R-0P1C0 (non-compression resistant CFRP) are in good agreement with R-EXP up to $\pm 6\delta_y$ cycle. However, R-0P1C1 better approximates R-EXP behavior up to $\pm 8\delta_y$ compared to R-0P1C0 which has faster decrease in capacity upon CFRP failure after $\pm 6\delta_y$. R-0P1C1 provided better estimates of R-EXP results for both the horizontal load capacity and ductility, as shown in Table 6. Hence, R-0P1C1 is adopted as the final FEA model for the reinforcement case of this study.

For the repair models, the positive loading behavior generated from S-0P1C1 (compression-resistant CFRP) and S-0P1C0 (non-compression resistant CFRP) models approximate the S-EXP specimen's behavior on the positive loading side. However, only the initial rigidity and re-yielding after repair were captured for the negative loading side. By closely examining the envelope curves and tabulated parameters in Table 6, it can be inferred that S-0P1C0 is in better agreement with S-EXP than the S-0P1C1. Hence, S-0P1C0 is adopted as the final FEA model for the repair case.

Table 6: Comparison of maximum horizontal load capacity and ductility (CFRP compression resistance model)

Model	(+) direction				(-) direction			
	Maximum Horizontal Load			Ductility	Maximum Horizontal Load			Ductility
	δ_{max}	H_{max} (kN)	H_{max} , % error	δ_{95}	δ_{max}	H_{max} (kN)	H_{max} , % error	δ_{95}
Reinforcement Case								
R-EXP	$+8\delta_y$	479.5	-	$+8.0\delta_y$	$-7\delta_y$	-462.0	-	$-8.0\delta_y$
R-0P1C1	$+7\delta_y$	480.4	0.2%	$+8.0\delta_y$	$-6\delta_y$	-478.8	3.7%	$-7.4\delta_y$
R-0P1C0	$+6\delta_y$	468.4	2.3%	$+6.9\delta_y$	$-5\delta_y$	-461.9	0.0%	$-6.2\delta_y$
Repair Case								
S-EXP	$+7\delta_y$	453.2	-	$+8.1\delta_y$	$-4\delta_y$	-409.0	-	$-5.5\delta_y$
S-0P1C1	$+8\delta_y$	475.6	4.9%	$+9.0\delta_y$	$-6\delta_y$	-403.4	1.4%	$-8.5\delta_y$
S-0P1C0	$+7\delta_y$	446.1	1.6%	$+8.4\delta_y$	$-6\delta_y$	-393.2	3.9%	$-8.0\delta_y$

COMPARISON OF EXPERIMENTAL AND ANALYTICAL MODEL

Buckling behavior comparison

In this section, the buckling deformations generated from the FEA were compared to the experimental results. Figure 12 illustrates the buckling modes for each case at final loading.

In the unreinforced case experiment, an outward bulge was observed from $h = 350$ mm to $h = 400$ mm from the column base, as shown in Figure 12a. The maximum buckling deformation is equal to 12 mm at $h = 400$ mm from the column base. The N-0P1 model reproduced this with an outward bulge occurring at the same location along the column height with maximum deformation of 15 mm, as shown in Figure 12d.

In the reinforcement case experiment, no significant buckling deformation was evident by visual inspection (refer to Figures 12b and 12e). But upon further investigation of the strain data, it was found that minimal debonding started to occur from $h = 400$ mm to $h = 500$ mm from the base after the displacement load equal to $-6\delta_y$. At larger displacements for R-EXP, cracks were observed in the circumferential direction and the majority of these occurred between $h = 300$ mm and $h = 450$ mm from the base, which corresponds to the range of the thick CFRP layers. The R-0P1C1 model was able to capture the CFRP damage; however, the analytical model produced more pronounced inward buckling from $h = 400$ mm to $h = 550$ m. This area corresponds to the transition region from thick- to thin-layer CFRP.

In the repair case experiment, a fracture sound was observed at $-7\delta_y$ loading caused by a significant crack that occurred in the circumferential direction at the negative loading side. At final loading, severe tensile damage occurred from $h = 350$ mm to $h = 450$ mm from the base. The damage circumferentially propagated up to the axis perpendicular to the loading direction at the same height as shown in Figure 12c and 12f. S-0P1C0 model was able to reproduce the same buckling behavior which is a combination of inward and outward buckling from $h = 350$ mm to $h = 450$ mm from the base; however, the deformations from the analytical model are more prominent and are approximately 5 to 10 mm larger than the measured values from the experiment. Upon further examination of Figure 12f, it can be noticed that the circumferential propagation of the damage at the negative loading side and the accumulated inward buckling at the positive loading side were also reproduced by the model.

Given the comparisons above, it can be concluded that the final FEA models provide substantial approximation of the buckling behavior observed in the cyclic loading tests.

Figure 12: Buckling modes at final loading

Horizontal load-displacement behavior and energy absorption comparison

The resulting load-displacement curves from the experimental study and the final FEA models from the parametric studies are shown in Figure 13. The comparison of maximum horizontal loads and energy absorption rates from the experimental study and the implemented FEA models are summarized in Table 7. The energy absorption rate is calculated separately for the analytical and experimental results. As noted in earlier discussion, the implemented models overestimate the energy absorption capacity of the reinforced and repaired columns.

With set criteria on horizontal load capacity and ductility, the adopted CFRP compression resistance models for the R- and S-models are different. This can be associated with the limited considerations for the CFRP failure, wherein the debonding progress was not considered. For the reinforcement case, accounting for the CFRP compression resistance best approximated the experimental results since the specimen did not undergo significant CFRP failure and debonding. Thus, the CFRP's compression resistance was sustained up to larger displacement cycles. For the repair case, the non-compression resistant assumption had better agreement with the experimental results. This can be attributed to the debonding that started to occur at $\pm 2\delta_y$ prior to tensile failure at $-7\delta_y$. Hence, CFRP lost its compression resistance at earlier loading cycles. Since the progression of debonding up to failure was not accounted for in the model, the closest approximation that the current FEA models can produce is that of S-0P1C0. In conclusion, improved models can be created by considering debonding to address the overestimation on the energy absorption and to improve the approximation of load displacement behavior as failure progresses, especially at larger displacements.

Figure 13: Summary of horizontal load-displacement relationships

Table 7: Summary of experimental and analytical results

Model		Maximum Horizontal Load (kN)			Energy absorption rate	
		Experiment	Analysis	% _{error}	Experiment	Analysis
N	+	418.4	406.3	2.9%	1.00	1.00
	-	417.3	404.3	3.1%	1.00	1.00
R	+	479.5	480.4	0.2%	1.07	1.24
	-	462.0	478.8	3.7%	1.13	1.30
S	+	453.2	446.1	1.6%	0.90	1.09
	-	409.0	393.2	3.9%	1.00	1.10

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the cyclic loading test results were used to assess the retrofitting effect of externally bonded CF sheets to steel circular columns. Parametric studies were conducted to produce FEA models that can adequately evaluate the horizontal load-displacement behavior, energy absorption rate, and buckling behavior observed from the experimental study:

1. The results showed that proposed CF sheet configuration, composed of thick- and thin-layer CFRP, is an effective retrofitting technique in terms of buckling suppression and performance recovery for both the reinforcement and repair cases of circular steel columns.
2. Base condition modeling significantly affects the initial rigidity, pre-yield behavior, and maximum horizontal load capacity of the steel columns. The explicit base condition modeling which accounts for P- Δ effects can provide better approximations of the column's elastic and pre-yield branches compared to the traditional fixed base model.
3. Finite element analysis using more accurate numerical approaches provides a better representation of the column behavior for the reinforcement and repair cases. However, the implemented models can still be improved in terms of the material representation of both the steel and CFRP to prevent overestimation of the energy absorption capacity of the specimen.
4. Upon monitoring the generated critical CFRP shell stresses with respect to the limiting CFRP tensile and compressive stress capacities along with the envelope curves, it was observed that the starting point of strength degradation coincides with the load increments at which CFRP failure occurs. This behavior observed from the analytical models is consistent with the observed damage and buckling progression in the experimental study.

5. The implemented FEA models for both reinforcement and repair cases can adequately approximate the behavior observed from the experiments. This is represented by the minimal errors computed for the maximum horizontal load capacity, and the similarities between buckling modes and CFRP damage locations.

For future works, more accurate yield functions and hardening rules can be utilized to produce better results in terms of the load-displacement behavior of the unreinforced steel specimen. A more detailed representation of the composite action between the CF sheets and resin matrix can be incorporated into the FEA models to account for different modes of failure of the externally bonded reinforcement, such as CFRP cracking and debonding. This can help improve the approximation of the overall specimen behavior and identify the expected column behavior at distinct stages and types of CFRP failure.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.